

USING ARTISTIC LITERATURE IN FORMING THE CREATIVE SKILLS OF PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS

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Abstract. *The dissertation reveals the content and essence of the formation of creative abilities of primary school pupils based on fiction, the goals and objectives of its implementation, organizational and methodological rules, effective means and methods. Specialists in this field can use methodological recommendations for the formation of creative abilities of younger schoolchildren in their teaching activities. The role of books and fiction is incomparable in penetrating into the depths of the hearts of the younger generation, expanding their worldview, developing their minds and moving towards their dreams. In the world, it is of particular importance to conduct research work on the methodological improvement of the formation of creative abilities of younger schoolchildren, strengthening book reading, creative activity of students, the development of a natural science worldview.*

Keywords: *creativity, ability, activity, innovation, discovery, creative approach, emotional attitude.*

It is necessary to understand the potential of each child, encourage his development and guide him correctly. If this ability is not developed or properly directed, it may disappear after years. The implementation of the improvement of the methodology for the formation of creative abilities of primary school pupils based on fiction, the conduct of new research works and their application in practice is always one of the topics that cause discussion. Therefore, the topic of the dissertation was chosen as "Improving the methodology for the formation of creative abilities of primary school pupils based on fiction". Appropriate scientific conclusions and recommendations have been developed based on the application of the method of improving the creative abilities of primary school pupils based on fiction in the educational process.

Introduction. In building the future of the Republic of Uzbekistan, educating the young generation as a person with high knowledge, intellectual potential, and high creative ability is the priority task of today[1]. The role of books and fiction is incomparable in reaching the depths of the hearts of the young generation, expanding their worldview, growing their minds, and moving towards their dreams. It is necessary to understand the potential of every child, to encourage its development and to guide it properly. Developing the creative abilities of elementary school pupils through fiction, doing new research and applying them in practice has always been one of the topics that cause discussion [2].

The purpose of the research: to develop relevant scientific conclusions and recommendations based on the application of the method of improving the creative abilities of primary school pupils based on fiction in the educational process.

Research object and used methods

As the object of the research, fiction literature, age-appropriate resources for primary school pupils, mainly works that shape creativity were selected. The methods of classification, classification, historical-comparative, contextual, complex and functional analysis were used to clarify the research topic.

The obtained results and their analysis

We need to know the theoretical and practical aspects that are considered important in the process of teaching and educating students in primary school. First of all, we need to know these pedagogical and psychological problems:

1. the formation of the student's personality and the content of labor and educational activities;
2. the level of psychological development of the pupil;
3. socio-psychological characteristics of the pupil's personality.

His innate abilities and talents are important in the formation of a child's intellectual potential. It is the child who has the innate ability to quickly understand and intensively absorb all the educational, educational, and professional teachings of adults. Not everyone has this kind of talent, innate talent. Therefore, it is necessary to form and develop the ability. For this, great perseverance is required from the teacher, parents, and the public. In the process of work and study, the student's ability awakens and his abilities continue to grow. The concept of talent has the same meaning as the concept of ability.

As creative abilities are formed and developed, patience and restraint are required from the elementary school teacher. Factors that negatively affect students' creative abilities:

- a) state of stress;
- b) state of high anxiety;
- c) time limit;
- d) desire to quickly find a solution;
- e) strict limitation;
- f) insecurity arising from previous failures;
- g) state of fear.

The knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired in the educational institution are not enough for students to achieve their goals. They should constantly search, be active in the process of social relations. We cannot say that students who cannot learn general subjects are incompetent. The task of us teachers is to deeply study the age and psychological characteristics of each child, to know their interests and desires, and to take pedagogical measures when we know them. Any activity of the teacher greatly affects the mental, aesthetic, physical, moral and willful development of the child. Parents and teachers should create the necessary conditions for students to be creative, only then will new inventions and discoveries begin to appear in society.

By assigning tasks to pupils' workbooks, what they learned was reinforced and supplemented. Such analyzes bring students closer to the book, help the child to fully understand and read the book instead of just reading it. Months and contests are organized every month of the academic year in order to identify and further develop children's abilities in science, culture, sports, art and other fields, and to increase their knowledge about these fields. Among them are "Husnikhat", "Best Artist", "Best Reader", "Best Mathematician". The final part of the monthly and contests in the form of a report was held in May at the "Recognition" event, and the winning students were awarded with nominations. Months, contests, various meetings, events, intellectual games, open classes, open educational classes that are held outside the classroom also help the development of the student's abilities, talents, and creativity, and increase their interests. He educates him as a free, independent thinker and enriches his spirituality. Types of creativity are determined by inventive activity: the work of an organizer, inventor, scientific and artistic work,

etc. The necessary opportunities for creative activity are related to social relations. Currently, the educational reforms that are being carried out with the honor of independence are aimed at training highly qualified personnel who can creatively approach their activities and contribute to the rapid development of science, technology, production, and art. depends. Therefore, it is the highest goal of pedagogues like us to cultivate creative, talented, aspiring and necessary personnel suitable for our time.

At the same time that the honorable president of our country is paying attention to the implementation of consistent reforms in the development of education, it is important to educate elementary school pupils to become well-educated, intelligent patriots in all aspects, to identify their talents and abilities and to direct them correctly. development is an urgent task. The role and importance of fiction in developing the talent of primary school students is incomparable.

The decision of the leader of our country on September 13, 2017 to further develop the culture of reading is not in vain, because the book is a product of human development, the little reader who reads it understands the difference between good qualities and bad vices, the inner experiences of the heroes of the work, and develops his written oral speech. Vocabulary expands. A pupil who loves books can master all subjects well. Reading books is a factor that forms the spirituality of students. It is possible to find out what a nation is like from its spirituality. The correct formation of the nation's spirituality is related to the correct implementation of the educational process. Educating the growing young generation as book lovers is important for the future of our tomorrow.

A new, creative approach is required in the development of students' creative abilities through fiction.

The role of fiction in the education of pupils and the formation of their creative abilities:

- the influence of reading books, dictionary works, didactic games and fiction literature on musical abilities in the development of creative abilities of pupils;
- the role of fiction in the development of various forms of creative abilities;
- The role of books in teaching pupils to think independently;
- The impact of literary works on the reader to engage in free, active communication, express an independent opinion;
- Forms the communication culture, internal and external speech, vocabulary, and aesthetic culture of students of literary literature.

Creation of necessary conditions for the development of the pupil's creative abilities in the educational process, consistent and regular use of didactic games, exercises and assignments, independent work, creating problem situations by the teacher, pupils' attention to these problems Giving students the opportunity to find their own solutions, making students interested in reading books will have a good effect on the development of their creative abilities. [7,8]

It is appropriate to perform the following tasks in the classroom and in extracurricular reading lessons.

1 To consider the possibility of gradually introducing each beginning reader to the increasingly complex independent reading activity in order to acquire the experience of personal behavior suitable for this social role.

2. Identifying its central and additional elements when building the foundations of the organizational-methodical system of the independent reading course.

3. Establishing interaction and interdependencies between the elements of this system.

4. To determine the leading teaching methods in the formation of independent reading.

By reading a book, the following creative abilities are formed:

1. Along with the education of a student who has read a book, his creativity develops.

2. Artistic expressiveness of the work affects children's thinking ability and emotions.

Increases knowledge about the environment.

3. The main criterion of the material is the correct selection of a literary work that is connected with different aspects of life, oriented to the ideological and spiritual content, suitable for elementary school students and increases their knowledge and vocabulary. It has a good effect on the emergence of creative abilities.

4. A pupil who reads and memorizes poetry learns to speak clearly and fluently, to use words in their proper place. A student who tries to recite memorized poems over and over again becomes interested in writing poems. Small poems can be practiced, but the main thing is that the hidden ability in it has come to the surface.

5. Pupils who are interested in writing poetry should first be taught to find rhyming words. For example, happiness-throne, youth-head-cook-sun, klam-korkam, book-sun.

6. It is necessary to explain the spiritual connection and contrast between the words. After that, teaching comparative simile is very effective in developing the ability to write poetry.

7. Reading a poem, explaining its content, singing it to a certain tone will bring out the pupils' musical abilities.

8. Gradual transition from small-scale works to large-scale works, use of appropriate works will have a great effect on the development of creative abilities of students of junior school age.

Emotional attitude of elementary school pupils towards the literary hero means that they imitate heroes with good qualities. Children use their personal and moral concepts to evaluate the characters of the play. They often use the concepts of goodness, bravery, diligence and correctness as moral qualities. At first, their vocabulary may not be enough to describe other qualities of the heroes of the work. However, as a result of more careful reading, they will have the ability to describe the hero in all aspects. Ability is a feature that explains the speed and ease of acquiring knowledge and skills related to the successful performance of any activity. The role of poetry books in improving the pupil's creative ability is incomparable. A student who reads and memorizes poetry learns to speak clearly and fluently, and to use words in their proper place. The world of poetry binds the reader to it like an ohangrabo. A student who tries to recite memorized poems over and over again becomes interested in writing poems. Small poems can be practiced, but the main thing is that the hidden ability in it has come to the surface. Students interested in writing poetry should first be taught to find rhyming words. For example, happiness-throne, youth-head-cook-sun, klam-korkam, book-sun. It is necessary to explain the semantic connection and contrast between the words. After that, it is necessary to teach comparative analogy. It is recommended that you read more fiction in order to be able to use words and sentences appropriately in poetry.

Conclusion

1. From primary grades, which are the basis of a mature personnel training system, it is necessary to make effective use of out-of-class reading lessons in developing pupils' creative abilities, to use interactive methods such as "Venn diagram", "T" method forms to get them interested in reading fiction. .

2. In order to teach pupils to think independently in the process of analyzing a work of art, recommended materials and didactic games for problem research, independent work method should be suitable for educational material, age and psychological characteristics of students, knowledge levels must

3. It is necessary to theoretically and methodologically improve the system of developing the creative abilities of primary school pupils.

4. The texts provided in the native language and reading literacy textbooks can also be effectively used to prepare students for PIRLS international assessment programs.

5. It is necessary to integrate native language and reading literacy textbooks and music, natural science and technology textbooks in developing pupils' creative abilities.

6. It is necessary to improve extracurricular reading classes, to use works that develop pupils' creative abilities.

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